

ENSURING EMPLOYMENT OF LABOR RESOURCES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract. *In the article, the characteristics of the formation of labor resources in agriculture, regardless of the form of ownership, the need to follow the requirements of the market economy and the need to ensure the employment of labor resources are seen. The potential of a person to work has been determined. Conclusions are given on the effective use of labor resources, reproduction of labor force regardless of the ownership forms of the economy in agricultural production, and justification of the main factor of the production process.*

Keywords: *agriculture, labor resources, market, market economy, labor force, reproduction, market relations, farm, peasant economy, labor market, methods of evaluating labor resources, population employment and unemployment, determination of the optimal amount of labor resources, provision of labor resources, labor potential.*

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of market economy relations, the reproduction of labor forces in agriculture is the main source of their provision and effective management of jobs in agriculture.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, it is necessary to ensure the creation of 500,000 new jobs within the framework of state programs and through the development of entrepreneurship. Business entities and new jobs created in each industry, sector, region and district will be the most important criteria for evaluating the activities of the leaders of these organizations. [1]

URGENCY OF THE PROBLEM

Agricultural production sectors are the sector that ensures the stable development of our national economy. Agriculture supplies not only the consumer products needed by the population, but also the agricultural raw materials needed by the processing industries. Production efficiency in agricultural sectors depends on the costs per unit of production and the quality of the products. The effectiveness of these economic indicators depends on the organization of labor resources in agriculture and their effective use, and it expresses its relevance.

STUDY OF THE PROBLEM BY SCIENTISTS

The study of problems of the organization of labor resources in agriculture and their effective use by scientists from foreign countries proves once again how relevant it is. By them, a person's personal creativity, creative ability, labor resources, saving labor [2], labor market, methods of evaluating labor resources, population employment and unemployment [3], formation of the labor market, helping the unemployed [4], determining the optimal amount of labor resources [5] motivation work [6], provision of labor resources [7], human capital of the worker [8], effective development of all branches of agriculture [9].

The formation of labor resources in agricultural sectors in market conditions has its own characteristics, and it is important to study it theoretically and practically.

Regardless of the ownership structure of the economy in agricultural production, the reproduction of labor power is the main factor of the production process and ensures its constant

relevance. In the conditions of market economy relations, it is necessary to study reproduction in agricultural sectors as follows.

First of all, it represents the basis of production of natural resources and covers mainly underground resources, agriculture and forestry. Secondly, it is related to the production of ready-to-consume or semi-consumable products developed by industries that extract natural resources, and thirdly, the service industries are trade, transport, communication, education, health, science, culture, household and utility services. divided into parts.

As a result of the development of the process of social reproduction, the main sector of the economy, the production of agricultural products based on the effective use of natural resources in agriculture, and industrial enterprises that re-produce them have developed, and in the conditions of market economy relations, the service sector has a superior level of development compared to these two sectors. must have. In developed countries, the size of this economic sector is 60-80 percent in the provision of social and personal services for well-being on the basis of satisfaction.

Service industries, which are the third sector of the national economy, are also developing in Uzbekistan. The growth of the working-age population among the urban population during this period was 7.7 percent, while this indicator was 10.9 percent among the rural population. For working adults, this figure was 10.9 and 43.4 percent. Women employed in the economy increased by 13.9 percent in 2011-2020. and men increased by 27.2 percent. 18.3% of those employed in the economy on January 1, 2020 were employed in state institutions, and 81.7% were employed in non-state institutions [10].

Employment of labor in agricultural production sectors, based on free competition, is the main reason why it is considered a commodity, and the owner hires him to use his ability to work. The worker's ability to work is a commodity, it is considered a special commodity and is the main source of income. As a way to ensure the effective development of the market economy, it is necessary to implement the reproduction of production forces in agriculture, and to provide jobs to the part of them capable of working, in exchange for the development of material and non-material production sectors related to agriculture.

It is necessary to prevent unemployment in agriculture on the basis of sustainable development of its branches, on the basis of the creation of necessary jobs and production of production forces according to demand.

To prevent the existing problems in the social and economic development of our republic based on the perspective of economic sectors, including agricultural sectors, and the demand for labor necessary for education, health care, housing, communal economy, and construction from intangible sectors based on supply and demand. negative effects can be reduced.

In the conditions of current market relations in our republic, the working age limits are defined as follows. The lower limit of working age is 16 years, the upper limit is 59 years for men and 54 years for women. When they reach this age, they have the right to rest. At the same time, men and women who are employed in certain production sectors and non-material production sectors will have the right to retire and receive a pension based on their length of service 5-10 years earlier compared to the youth of the pension set for all.

The main reason for this is the effect of high mental and physiological pressure on a person in some areas. The labor resources do not include disabled persons of the first and second groups, but persons with disabilities recognized by the state and persons who are working on retirement also make up the labor resources of our country.

The main reason for the decrease of active women employed in agriculture is that they move to work in non-material production sectors in rural areas.

Ensuring the prevention of unemployment among the rural population in the republic is related to the level of organization of production in agricultural sectors, and the training of personnel in the specialties necessary for its effective development is the most urgent problem.

The demand for manpower for the agricultural sector is constantly changing based on supply and demand. The main reason for this is the freedom of economic competition, which can ensure its efficiency as a result of the production of competitive products in agricultural production. In the reproduction of labor forces, production entities based on non-state ownership, not only the state, should carry out the necessary personnel training and employment at their own expense.

Employment of labor resources in agriculture is the main indicator of the production process. Employment of labor resources in agriculture occurs in the following cases:

- it is expressed in full-time or part-time employment of the labor force capable of working in the agricultural sector, earning wages for themselves and income for property owners based on their work;

- receiving income as a result of the employment of labor resources working on their estates without payment of labor;

- labor resources can be seen in the way that some private property subjects receive wages commensurate with their work based on the performance of certain works.

Labor resources are mainly used in two ways: from private estates or at enterprises of agricultural production estates. In the current market conditions, their use in other sectors of the economy is also widespread. The main part of the labor resources in the conditions of the market economy conducts its activities in the form of wage labor. Work fees are paid in cash or in kind in the form of products grown by them in agriculture.

The differences between labor resources in hiring labor or working in one's own private farm are as follows. If a hired worker seeks to get more wages for his work, the owner of a job employed in a private economy seeks to increase the level of profit obtained by reducing the production costs per unit of output through his work.

If there is a part of the population capable of working physically and mentally at the first stage of the transformation of labor resources into the labor force in agriculture, they will not become a full-fledged agricultural labor force without the means of production, the necessary equipment and technologies.

In order to turn them into a labor force, they become a labor force due to the fact that they are put into work in the form of labor resources, taking into account their professional skills and qualifications.

As a result, the labor force employed in agriculture, as a result of working on the basis of their ability to work, not only creates consumer products in their natural state, but also their value. The transformation of labor resources employed in the agricultural production process into labor force has its own characteristics. These features are expressed in:

- the seasonal classification of labor demand in agriculture;

- labor resources become labor force only when the production process is carried out in agriculture, and the rest of the time they remain in the state of labor resources;

- the seasonality of the production process in agriculture depends on the organization of labor requirements depending on the production season.

Labor resources with the ability to work in agriculture are distributed according to the economic development of economic sectors and regions, representing those capable of working.

Therefore, labor potential has a broad meaning, it forms labor resources, represents the labor force as a factor of production and is the main factor that ensures economic growth as a subject of social relations. Labor potential is a factor of economic potential, which can be used only through labor. Labor potential is the main category of economic potential in economic practice, and it can be considered as the main factor of economic potential based on the fact that it can be ensured that its quantitative and qualitative level is realized based on the material, organizational and socio-economic conditions.

In the conditions of market relations, the reproduction of the labor force is not enough to satisfy their economic demands, but also to increase their labor productivity by increasing their scientific and professional potential, in order to ensure that the products of their labor are competitive in the consumer market, along with the organization of their production and residential infrastructures at the level of demand. It is possible to increase the efficiency of enterprises based on the reduction of production costs. As a result, it is necessary to determine the labor force at the level necessary for the production of employment, and redistribute the excess labor force at the level of sectors or regions.

The reproduction of labor resources in agriculture can be achieved not only by increasing the population at the expense of birth, but also at the expense of increasing the population and labor resources, increasing the efficiency of the rural population and labor resources by providing them with health, preventing diseases, and extending the life span based on the demand level of working and living conditions of the rural population. In the conditions of agriculture, it ensures the growth of material funds of farms, the growth of labor productivity and wages. based on the effective use of scientific and technical achievements in production, reducing the time of employment of the labor force in work activities also satisfies the demand for additional labor forces.

In the conditions of market relations based on free competition, the reproduction of labor force in rural areas should be carried out by the state and the farms interested in it, based on the law of supply and demand.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Based on the study of the characteristics of the formation of labor resources in agriculture, the following conclusions can be reached:

- the formation of labor resources in the agricultural sector and their effective use depends on the land area that can be used for labor and natural resources, which are its main means, and the development of industrial re-production of agricultural products and intangible services in rural areas;

shows that it does not fully satisfy the demand for providing jobs to the economically active population in the agricultural sector;

- the employment of labor resources is the main indicator of agriculture, full employment can be achieved in exchange for the industrial processing of agricultural products and the development of services in various social spheres.

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